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Sound Memory as Dramaturgy of Time: Compositional Dramaturgies for Temporal Perception in Musical Performance

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Abstract This article explores the role of sound memory as a generative principle for constructing a non-linear dramaturgy of musical time. Drawing on Bergson's concept of *durée*, Ricoeur's narrative memory, and the sonic dramaturgy theories of Chion and LaBelle, memory is examined as an active and performative process both compositional and perceptual. Through analyses of Berio's *Sinfonia*, Harvey's *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco*, and Romitelli's *An Index of Metals*, the study identifies three temporal strategies: cultural palimpsest, spiritual transfiguration, and perceptual persistence. The investigation extends to *Somax²* (IRCAM) as a model of algorithmic memory, generating musical form through continuous re-actualization and interaction between human and machine temporalities. The compositional case study *Abissum II (racines)* concludes the research, revealing memory as dramaturgical substance, where echoes and returns from Gesualdo, Monteverdi, and Romitelli shape a multilayered temporality. Sound memory thus emerges as a living form of time, transforming composition and performance into spaces of resonance between past and present.

Keywords Sound memory, Temporal dramaturgy, Sonic perception, Algorithmic memory, Intermedia temporality

1. Introduction

Composition, by its very definition, is an act concerned with the organisation of time. It constitutes a chronological suspension in which the composer must conceive an

architecture capable of containing the elements necessary to shape sonic perception within the moment of performance.

In contemporary music, a multitude of factors contribute to the craft of composition, whether instrumental or oriented towards the broader sphere of intermedial possibilities. Among these, *memory* stands as a formal pillar of the acoustic experience, understood not merely as a symbolic or thematic reference but as a living element capable of enabling the coexistence of multiple temporalities in favour of innovative and original dramaturgical structures.

Sound memory can therefore be investigated as a compositional strategy that guides the listener towards a non-chronological and non-linear perception of time in musical performance. Within this exploratory framework lies the intersection of various fields of study, in particular those concerned with contemporary music composition and the aesthetics of perception.

This investigation unfolds in two directions. The first, theoretical, is grounded in a re-examination of Bergson's concept of duration, Ricoeur's writings on narrative temporality, Voegelin's thought conceives the perception of sound not as a fixed object and the notion of sonic dramaturgy developed by M. Chion. It then proceeds with the analysis of works that adopt memory as a structural principle, such as Luciano Berio's *Sinfonia*, Jonathan Harvey's *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco*, and Fausto Romitelli's audio-visual opera *An Index of Metals*.

The second, analytical, engages with the introduction of SOMAX², a system of generative co-improvisation

developed within the research framework of IRCAM, where the concept of memory is modelled computationally to produce real-time sonic outputs. This process fosters the creation of an active algorithmic memory capable of rewriting the temporal dimension of performance and execution.

Departing from this approach, which explores the singular relationship between human and machine, the analysis of the original composition *Abissum II (racines)* by Manuela Guerra for ensemble, considers memory as a formal matrix of the present and the past, capable of generating echoes and returns.

Through the exposition of the relationship between compositional memory and generative memory, this study aims to emphasise contemporary performance as a potential theatre of temporal coexistence, where past and present may merge not only through mechanisms shaped by formal principles drawn from musical literature but also through processes that foster the creation of a dramaturgy of sound that generates, transforms, and transcends.

2. Philosophical Context

The relationship between time and memory is among the most intimate and intrinsic to music, which embodies their deepest roots.

In *Durée et simultanéité*, Henri Bergson establishes a distinction between measurable, external, chronological time and lived, qualitative time, which manifests itself as duration^[1]. From this perspective, memory is not a static archive but an active process that sustains the continuity of consciousness, intertwining past and present within an uninterrupted flow. Transposed into the sonic domain, this conception suggests that every sound carries within itself a residue of what has already been, while anticipating what is yet to come in the immediate future of musical composition. Sonic perception thus becomes a field in which memory operates as a generative and constitutive force.

Paul Ricoeur, in *Temps et récit*, deepens this tension between lived temporality and narrated temporality, emphasising the role of memory as a faculty capable of shaping time itself^[2]. The temporal line of narrative is therefore not a mere chronological succession but rather an intricate weave that reactivates the past within the present, generating new configurations. Within this framework, the sonic experience can be interpreted as a narrative practice that does not reproduce linear time in its chronological sense, but transforms it into an aesthetic experience through the identification of individual and collective, subjective and, insofar as possible, objective sound memories.

From the perspective of acoustic perception, Salomé Voegelin, in *Listening to Noise and Silence*, insists upon the profoundly temporal nature of listening: sound never presents itself as a stable object but as an event existing solely in the moment of its perception. Listening thus

becomes the locus where temporality is constructed: each sound refers to others, takes root within the listener's physical body, and generates a perception of the present continuously permeated by the past^[3]. Memory, in this sense, is not merely what induces recollection, but what grants access to the thresholds of individual perception.

Within this context, musicology is interrogated by Michel Chion, who in *Audio-Vision* demonstrates how sound, particularly in relation to the image, acts as an organising principle of perceptual temporality^[4]. The phenomenon of sonic anachronism, through which a sound may evoke times different from those suggested by the images it accompanies, reveals how memory intervenes to generate temporal meaning through the signifier. Discussing Alvin Lucier's work *I Am Sitting in a Room*, LaBelle observes: "Lucier's *I Am Sitting in a Room* accentuates subjective experience as inherently in process; the compounding of his voice, through recording and rerecording, opens up the possibility of pure speech [...] revealing sound as always in process." Here, sound becomes a generator of stratified temporality: each echo and resonance transforms the acoustic space into a new temporal dimension, producing a performative presence that challenges both the linearity of time and the fixity of space^[5].

Within this framework, one may therefore affirm that sound memory in musical performance is not merely an evocative or mnemonic function but a dramaturgical device. It constructs time as an aesthetic experience, transforming chronological linearity into stratification and simultaneity, and thereby opens the performative space to diverse forms of temporality. This theoretical framework provides the foundation for analysing compositional cases in which memory becomes the living material of the artistic process.

3. Memory: An Architecture of Time in Compositional Works

3.1 Luciano Berio: *Sinfonia* (1968)

Luciano Berio's *Sinfonia* stands as one of the most emblematic works of twentieth-century music, not only for its formal innovations but above all for the way it redefines the very concept of musical memory. Particularly significant in this regard is the third movement (*In ruhig fliessender Bewegung*), constructed upon the *Scherzo* of Gustav Mahler's Second Symphony, which marks a turning point in the conception of composition as a temporal palimpsest.

In this movement, Berio, adopts Mahler's material as the structural fabric upon which he layers quotations and fragments drawn from a vast spectrum of musical traditions, ranging from Bach and Beethoven to Debussy and Ravel, and extending to Schönberg, Webern, Stravinsky, Boulez, and Stockhausen. These sonic strata are interwoven with textual insertions drawn from authors such as Samuel

Beckett (*The Unnamable*), Claude Lévi-Strauss, and others. The result is not a mere collage but a genuine *polyphony of memory*: a complex interlacing of cultural and musical temporalities that coexist simultaneously within the acoustic space.

This operation does not consist of simple quotation but of the reactivation of fragments from tradition as living presences^[6]. The materials of the past are not reproduced statically but reinterpreted and placed in dialogue with one another, generating new constellations of meaning. Memory, in this context, does not function as a repository in stasis but as a dynamic and productive process.

From the standpoint of perception, the listener is placed in an ambivalent position. On the one hand, familiar references to the historical repertoire and musical literature (Mahler, Debussy, Ravel, and others) are recognisable; on the other, these same fragments appear transfigured, suspended within a present that distorts and overlaps them, altering their contours. This dialectic between recognition and disorientation produces an effect of simultaneous temporality, in which past and present merge and coexist.

Berio himself, in *Remembering the Future*, insists on memory as an active principle: “Because the awareness of the past is never passive and we do not want to be the obliging accomplices of a past that is always with us, that we nourish, and that never ends”^[7]. This conception finds in *Sinfonia* its most complete dramaturgical translation. The linear temporality of the symphonic tradition is replaced by a multidirectional web of correspondences and returns that dissolves classical progression and establishes a new temporal logic and texture.

This conception of memory as a transformative agent is reflected in Berio’s *Sinfonia* through a complex interplay of temporal and textual stratifications that transcends the logic of quotation and moves towards a genuine rewriting of the past. Rather than being merely evoked, the musical material is reworked, fragmented, and recontextualised within a metamusical framework. In this way, the work not only engages critically with the history of the symphonic form but also interrogates its underlying assumptions, placing memory at the core of a compositional process that is dynamic, reflective, and unmistakably contemporary.

The third movement of *Sinfonia* thus emerges as a paradigmatic laboratory of simultaneous temporality. Memory is not treated as mere quotation but as a compositional force capable of shaping the perception of time and transforming it into experience. The listener does not follow a linear narrative but is immersed in a network of memories that overlap, echo, and transform one another, generating a present in which the past persists as a living and operative tension.

In his analysis of the third movement of *Sinfonia*, Luciano Berio is shown to engage materials from the musical and literary past not as static quotations but as dynamic elements in an active compositional process. The

fragments he summons are re-activated, placed in dialogue, and set into relation in such a way that they generate a new temporal architecture: the movement becomes a network of cross-references, echoes and resonance rather than a linear sequence of citations. The voices are like characters in a musical drama conversing with one another and also having the power to affect the flow of the music^[8].

The opening bars (mm. 1-10) offer a privileged entry point into this poetics of time as active sound memory. Here, fragments drawn from Schoenberg (*Peripetie*), Debussy (*La Mer*, *Jeux de vagues*), and Mahler (Symphonies Nos. 2 and 4), together with agogic indications transformed into theatrical gestures (“nicht eilen, bitte”; “recht gemächlich”), are interwoven with a vocal texture built upon quotations from Beckett’s *The Unnamable*. This procedure transcends mere intertextuality or postmodern citation, taking the form of a genuine dramaturgy of time, in which every musical fragment acts as a vector of memory and temporal tension.

The choice of Mahler’s *Scherzo* from the Second Symphony as *cantus firmus*, present continuously throughout the movement even when imperceptible, establishes an underlying inner temporal line, an invisible current of continuity binding together the multiplicity of materials. It constitutes an “other” time, unsynchronised with the surface yet constantly active as a deep counter-time, as memory in action. This compositional mechanism becomes a musical reflection on the perception of time itself, transforming the past into a resonant present that returns not as static quotation but as an active and performative form.

Within this framework, sound memory assumes neither nostalgic nor documentary function; it is a living, malleable matter that deforms and transforms the sonic present. Berio thus constructs a palimpsestic temporality in which traces overwrite and interact, generating semantic and perceptual short circuits. The reference to Beckett, particularly to the voice of *The Unnamable* endlessly repeating “Keep going” becomes emblematic: time, like the voice, cannot cease but must continue to flow, even in the absence of direction or teleology. It is a fundamentally unstable time, inhabited by tensions between motion and stasis, between memory and oblivion, between stratification and discontinuity.

The transformation of musical directions into vocal gestures (agogic markings declaimed expressively by the singers), assumes special significance. What were originally functional indications become dramaturgical materials, sonic objects that question their own status. The score thus becomes a theatrical space in which the past is not merely evoked but re-enacted, embodied within performance. This theatre of memory is devoid of any celebratory intent; rather, it is pervaded by profound ambivalence, as the presence of the past destabilises the present, placing the listener in a state of perceptual and cognitive disorientation.

Berio therefore proposes not an ordered musical temporality but a field of temporal forces in which historical, musical, and textual materials coexist in a regime of dissonant co-presence. The result is a listening experience that does not

unfold *through* time but *within* time, producing a plural, non-linear perception deeply embedded in the historical consciousness of sound. In this sense, *Sinfonia* is not merely a work *about* memory: it is a work that writes memory into the very form of time, rendering audible the instability of history itself and of the subject who inhabits it.

3.2 Jhonatan Harrvey: *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* (1980)

Composed in 1980 at the studios of IRCAM, *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* stands as a seminal work in the history of electroacoustic music, owing to its capacity to integrate symbolic, technological, and perceptual dimensions within a unified temporal dramaturgy. The composition is founded upon two fundamental sonic materials: the voice of Jonathan Harvey's son, a boy soprano, and the sound of the great bell of Winchester Cathedral. These two elements convey memories of profoundly different natures: the voice, as a corporeal and biographical trace, fragile and individual and the bell, as a collective, ritual, and archaic sign.

The structure of the work is based on the reciprocal transformation of these two materials through advanced techniques of synthesis and. Neither the voice nor the bell is presented as an isolated sample. Rather, they are constantly manipulated, multiplied, and diffused throughout space, generating a sonic continuum that transcends the distinction between original source and technological elaboration. This process engenders a temporal dramaturgy founded not on progression but on fields of resonance, within which the materials recall, pursue, and merge into one another in a network of dynamic correspondences^[9].

Harvey himself explains that the aim of the work was to transform earthly sound into spiritual sound, intertwining the corporeal with the transcendent^[10]. This statement highlights how the composition constitutes a sonic meditation on life and death, already inscribed in the Latin motto engraved on the Winchester bell: *Mortuos plango, vivos voco, fulgura frango* ("I mourn the dead, I call the living, I break the lightning"). Here, sound memory functions not as a mere evocative faculty but as a transformative principle, an active force which, through electroacoustic processing, is continually renewed and reactivated in the present.

The work establishes an intricate interplay of heterogeneous temporalities: the ritual and cyclical time of the bell, rooted in collective memory; the fragile and transient time of the human voice, linked to biographical experience; the technological time produced by electronic manipulation, which fragments recomposes and transfigures the materials without end. The coexistence of these temporal dimensions generates a non-linear experience in which memory assumes a performative and generative agency.

From a technical standpoint, the work may be conceived as a form of spectral cartography in which time and memory cease to function as linear coordinates and instead unfold as

interdependent planes of transformation. A spectrogram of *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* would disclose this multidimensional structure: the inharmonic resonances of the bell and the vocal formants of the boy intertwine, overlap, and regenerate through successive layers, delineating a temporal topology closer to a spiral than to a line. This image embodies the concept of memory as a temporal morphology, functioning as an active continuum through which the past is continuously reinscribed within the sonic present.

The underlying logic of *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* may therefore be read as anticipating questions that are central to today's generative practices based on machine learning systems such as SOMAX². Whereas in Harvey's work sound memory is mediated by technology to give rise to an immersive and symbolic texture, in contemporary algorithmic systems memory is conceived as an active archive, capable of instantaneous reactivation. As noted by Saint-Germier, Canonne, and Fiorini (AIMC, 2024), SOMAX² inherits embodied generative constraints from the corpus itself, which translate into expressive conditions during musical generation. In both cases, memory - realised through electronic sound in Harvey's composition and through algorithmic processes in SOMAX² - fulfils the function of transforming sonic past into performative present.

This electroacoustic work, visionary for its time, thus demonstrates how sound memory, even prior to the advent of machine learning, could already be understood as a creative and temporal force capable of rewriting the very perception of time.

3.3 Fausto Romitelli: *An index of Metals* (2001)

An Index of Metals, described by Fausto Romitelli himself as a "psychedelic video-opera", stands among the most radical examples of immersive and temporal experience in contemporary music. Commissioned by the Fondation Royaumont, the work is conceived for soprano, instrumental ensemble, electronics, and video projection. It does not rely on a linear narrative principle but on a process of progressive perceptual saturation, enveloping the listener within an all-encompassing sensory continuum.

Romitelli's aesthetic is characterised by a profound fascination with deformed, saturated, and corroded sound materials, in which sound no longer functions solely as an organiser of time but becomes a perceptual substance capable of invading space and altering consciousness. The obsessive use of repetition and timbral deformation generates a form of hypnotic memory: the listener perceives the incessant return of sound, as though each instant were the echo of the preceding one. Memory does not here manifest itself as citation or symbol, but as a perceptual energy that transforms the present into a state of temporal trance.

The multimedia dimension plays a crucial role in this compositional architecture. The video projections created in collaboration with Paolo Pachini, together with the electronic treatment, produce a perceptual stratification of audiovisual nature. The intermedial dimension of the work becomes particularly evident in the fusion of images, sounds, and lights, which produces an effect of “audiovisual hypnosis”, wherein the chronological flow of time appears to be suspended. The work does not seek a climax or a final resolution; rather, it sustains the listener in a constant state of tension and perceptual immersion, within a present that continuously regenerates itself without interruption.

From the perspective of temporal dramaturgy, *An Index of Metals* replaces formal linearity with a circular and stratified experience. The sonic materials do not develop according to an evolutionary logic but undergo continuous transformation, as if arising from an immanent memory that ceaselessly brings them back to the surface in ever-renewed configurations. The resulting temporality is not narrative but qualitative, approaching what Henri Bergson defines as *durée*: a flow in which past and present coexist within the same state of consciousness. The work thus functions as a device that compels the listener to confront time not as a linear sequence but as an altered state of consciousness: a dilated present in which every instant is imbued with the memory of the sound that precedes it. In order to grasp the structural and spiritual substance of *An Index of Metals*, it is essential to examine how the work constructs its own sense of time through a series of sections that do not merely succeed one another, but coexist as distinct temporal states. The *Introduzione*, the first *Hellucination (Drowninggirl)*, the *Secondo Intermezzo* and *Adagio with Quarto Intermezzo*, as well as the *Finale with Cadenza*, do not delineate a linear succession of events; rather, they reveal a process of continuous transformation, in which memory and perception intertwine to generate a dynamic dramaturgy of sound and image.

The *Introduzione* is particularly significant in this regard. Despite its apparent simplicity, it encapsulates the aesthetic and structural principles that govern the entire composition. It unfolds through the obsessive recurrence of a single sonic object: the opening of *Shine on You Crazy Diamond* by Pink Floyd, sampled from a vinyl recording. This fragment, drawn from the collective memory of popular culture, is reanimated within a new acoustic and symbolic environment. Each repetition brings a subtle mutation, as orchestral layers progressively distort the original chord until its tonal identity dissolves into a dense spectrum of noise. What begins as an act of citation thus becomes an exploration of time itself, where remembrance is not the preservation of the past but its transformation into a living present^[11].

A similar process occurs within the visual domain. The video presents a slowly rotating grey circle that multiplies, accelerates, and thickens over time. The image mirrors the musical transformation, producing a sense of temporal compression in which duration appears to fold upon itself. The synchronization between sound and image does not function merely as correspondence but as a revelation of

their shared condition: both are temporal materials, shaped by processes of persistence, decay, and renewal.

Within this framework, *An Index of Metals* can be understood as a meditation on time and memory. Its form is not governed by progression or climax, but by the oscillation between repetition and metamorphosis. Time ceases to be a neutral measure and becomes a compositional substance, simultaneously eroding and generating meaning. Through this intricate dialogue of sound and image, Fausto Romitelli transforms musical experience into a reflection on memory itself, a temporal field where what returns is never identical, and where every echo marks the birth of something new.

Romitelli situates himself within a distinctive trajectory of reflection on memory, divergent from that of other composers of the late twentieth century. Whereas for Berio memory represents a repertoire to be reactivated, and for Harvey a spiritual symbol to be transfigured, in Romitelli it assumes the form of an intensive persistence.

4. SOMAX²: Algorithmic Memory as a Performative Device

The evolution of compositional and performative practices in contemporary music has been profoundly shaped by the emergence of interactive systems based on artificial intelligence and machine learning. Among these, Somax², developed within the electronic music studios of IRCAM, stands as one of the most significant examples of how memory can be conceived not as a static archive but as an algorithmic device capable of generating both time and form within performance.

Somax² is a multi-agent system designed for human-machine co-improvisation (Fiorini & Malt, 2023). Its architecture is articulated in four main phases:

- 1) Learn: the system learns from an audio or MIDI corpus provided by the musician or composer;
- 2) Model: the material is analyzed and segmented into coherent units (slices), organized into a structured memory;
- 3) Listen: the system listens in real time to the performer, identifying correspondences and activations within its internal memory;
- 4) Generate: it produces new sonic sequences based on the learned fragments, consistent with the corpus style yet always variable^[12].

In contrast to a simple database of samples, the system operates through an *active memory*: each fragment is not reproduced as a copy but reintegrated into a new performative context. Algorithmic memory therefore functions as a process of continuous reactualisation, in which the sonic past becomes generative material for the present of performance. Memory, in this framework, acts as

a performative agent. It is not a function of recall but a mechanism that intervenes actively in the interaction between musician and machine. Each performance generates new temporal trajectories, in which the stored fragments are reactivated and transformed.

This mode of operation transforms the very concept of musical time. Rather than a linear sequence, it articulates a plastic time, akin to the conception of time in theoretical physics, understood as a magnitude and dimension that adapts to the performer's choices and to the dynamics of co-improvisation.

Memory thus becomes a dynamic present, a field of possibilities continuously generating new configurations.

The study by Saint-Germier, Pachet, Esling, and Agostini introduces a key concept for understanding the scope of Somax²: that of *embodied generative constraints* (EGC)^[13]. Musical machine learning systems do not merely learn abstract patterns; they also inherit expressive and corporeal constraints from the human corpus on which they are trained. This implies that Somax²'s memory is not neutral but carries the traces of human gesture, the physicality of instruments, the stylistic decisions of the composer, and the interpretative sensibilities of the performer. These corporeal constraints become integral to the process of generation, transforming the algorithm into a kind of virtual body that embodies the musical memory of its source.

Such a phenomenological perspective overturns the notion of algorithmic memory as an abstract and impersonal process, demonstrating instead that computational memory, too, is inscribed within a body, a gesture, and a specific musical experience. From a compositional and performative standpoint, Somax² offers a radical model of memory as a generator of time. The past is not reproduced but transfigured: each reactivation produces new configurations in a process that may be described as one of creative memory.

When compared with the works discussed earlier, both affinities and divergences emerge. As in Berio, memory manifests as stratification, yet in Somax² it is automated and perpetually renewed. As in Harvey, it functions as a transformative principle, though here the transformation is governed by algorithms rather than spiritual symbols. And, as in Romitelli, memory induces a perceptual trance rather than linearity, though in Somax² this trance results from an interactive negotiation between performer and machine. This opens aesthetic and compositional perspectives that engage directly with the lineage of contemporary music. Somax² represents a pivotal stage in the history of sonic memory: from a human and symbolic function, it becomes an algorithmic and performative process. Memory is no longer merely citation (Berio), resonance (Harvey), or perceptual persistence (Romitelli), but *generative re-actualisation*.

Through the concept of *embodied generative constraints*, Somax² reveals that algorithmic memory is not detached from body or culture but is intrinsically shaped by them. What emerges is a new form of temporal dramaturgy, in which past and present intertwine in real time, within a performance where the notion of "live" opens itself to multiple paths and possibilities for exploration.

5. *Abissum II (Racines): Echoes of Time and Layered Memory*

In the final section of this inquiry, the perspective shifts from an external analytical framework to an internal compositional one. *Abysum II (racines)*, a composition for large ensemble - Flute, Clarinet in Bb (doubling Bass Clarinet in B), Trumpet in C, Two Percussionists (Symphonic bass drum, Snare drum, Vibraphone, Suspended cymbal, Medium tam-tam, Triangle), Piano and Strings (Vl. I, Vl. II, Vla., Vc.) - a work in a trilogy for large ensemble, constitutes an autonomous musical chapter a critical reflection in which the themes of sound memory, temporal perception, and the dramaturgy of sound are translated into living compositional material. The work unfolds within a hybrid space between density and subtraction, echo and rupture, opacity and transfiguration. Within it, memory does not evoke the past but becomes a plastic and dramaturgical substance, capable of shaping listening as a transformative experience.

The following analysis focuses on several structural and symbolic nuclei of the composition, with particular attention to how echoes of the past, that is, fragments, reminiscences, and transformed quotations, may act upon the perception of time and upon the formal articulation of the work.

The musical form draws inspiration from the pictorial work of Alberto Burri, particularly from one of the pieces belonging to the *Combustioni* series, *Combustione, legno* (1957), in which matter burns and tears apart^[14].

The sound itself is treated as a material to be wounded and transfigured. Fractures, stratifications, and scorched zones give shape to a dramaturgical narrative that, like a gentle suspicion, gradually empties itself of its shadows to make room for a luminous ascent free of compromise. It is a process of emergence in which the abyss becomes a necessary condition of origin, where listening may become an act of discovery and, above all, of resistance.

The structure of the composition is tripartite. In the first formal panel of *Abysum II (racines)* (bars 1-72), sound memory is activated not as mere evocation but as a structuring dramaturgical process, in which echoes and reminiscences operate as incisions upon a living and opaque material, layered through time. The entire section takes shape as a sonic traversal of darkness: a compact, irregular, and discontinuous acoustic matter, inspired by the torn and burned surfaces of Burri's *Combustioni*. Within this fragmentary sonic landscape, the presence of memory does

not manifest itself directly but hides, resurfaces, and deforms, like roots seeking light beneath a layer of raw earth. The strings, in particular, embody this density, constructing a sonic fabric in which memory becomes a broken gesture, a resistance to transparency, a material tension (Fig.1).

Figure 1. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), strings texture, bars 12-18. Score by the author (2025).

The composition is permeated by mnemonic reminiscences of works from the past, which not only evoke memory but also constitute its very structural fragments, assuming the role of foundational elements within the musical discourse. The first invocation of memory, therefore, is formed by fragments from *Moro, lasso, al mio duolo*, madrigal no. 17 by Carlo Gesualdo, taken from the *Sixth Book of Madrigals for Five Voices* (Fig.2).

Figure 2.C. Gesualdo, *Moro, lasso, al mio duolo*, from "Sesto libro de' madrigali a cinque voci", Naples, 1611. Public domain edition available at IMSLP – Petrucci Music Library, accessed October 2025.

The echoes of Gesualdo's madrigal *Moro, lasso, al mio duolo* emerge within the compositional fabric through two distinct levels. The first, more implicit, unfolds in the wind

instruments beginning at bar 21 and returns with rhythmic and temporal variations at bars 24, 29, and 32 (Fig.3), up to the false opening at bar 37.

Figure 3. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), bars 28-35. Score by the author (2025).

In these passages, the reference to Gesualdo is not so much harmonic as gestural: a sudden verticality, a kind of thrust into the material that gradually expands through repetition. It is a form of unconscious memory, operating beneath the surface. The second level, by contrast, introduces the explicit harmonic fragment: first foreshadowed at bar 48 (Fig.4), then clearly revealed at bar 52 in the winds, and finally reworked, first in its contracted version at bar 63 (Fig.5) and later in its expanded and incisive form in the strings at bar 69 (Fig.6).

Figure 4. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), bar 48. Score by the author (2025).

Figure 5. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), bar 63. Score by the author (2025).

Figure 6. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, bar 69-71. Score by the author (2025).

In these passages, the Gesualdo's chord is not quoted out of nostalgia but transformed into a scenic gesture, as though the past were imposing itself upon the surface of the present with an inescapable force.

The fragment employed, in its rhythmic and directional configuration, marked by a precise choice of durations and by homorhythmic articulation, functions as a structural anticipation, almost a prefigurative echo of a later event in the score that mirrors its formal logic in inverted form, first descending and then ascending. The relationship between these two moments is not limited to a mere thematic recall but establishes an additional perceptual layer in which memory and premonition overlap. This specular relationship, poised on the thread of compositional time, activates an internal mechanism of recognition that simulates a reflection, a musical image that extends itself, rooting in the present the anticipation of the future and, in the future, the resonance of what has already been heard.

In this section, sound memory becomes a structural material, defining a form that is not linear but circular and reflexive, composed of altered returns and presences that reveal themselves only in their dissolution. In this sense, the writing recalls the strategies analysed in Berio's *Sinfonia*, where Mahler's fragment functions as an invisible and pervasive *cantus firmus*, and in Harvey's *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco*, where voice and bell pursue and mirror one another in a continuous mnemonic flow. In *Abissum II* memory is neither fixed nor stable: it is a dynamic field of energies that transforms the perception of time from sequence into tension, from flow into substance.

A second type of temporal echo is activated through a transformed reprise taken from the first composition of the *Abyssum* trilogy, *Abyssum I (abissus invocat)*. Beginning at bar 48, the atmosphere takes on a more neurotic character: while the winds present the Gesualdian reminiscence, the strings move through broken gestures, descending glissandi, and lines that implode upon themselves, seeming to collapse under their own weight (Fig.7). These gestures evoke the gravitational poetics of the first *Abyssum*, in which sound falls, sinks, and dissolves.

Figure 7. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, bar 48. Score by the author (2025).

Memory here unfolds as a veiled thematic continuity, an invisible thread that connects the two works not through direct quotation, but through a shared tension.

At measure 56, the reminiscence becomes more explicit: the piano, orchestrated in synergy with the flute, recalls a timbral blend already explored in the previous work (Fig.8). Yet here it is recontextualised within a new sonic environment, where the original identity is altered, as though the memory itself had been transformed in its passage from one composition to the other.

Figure 8. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.15. Score by the author (2025).

This initial macro-section may thus be interpreted as a space in which memory surfaces, where every echo becomes a refraction, every return a perceptual transformation, and every fragment of the past a dramaturgical rewriting. In this perspective, time does not flow but pulses; it contracts and expands, settles and reactivates.

With measure 72 begins the second section of *Abissum II (racines)*, corresponding to the posthumous time of combustion, the rarefied and fragile space that follows the deflagration of matter (Fig.9).

Figure 9. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.21, Score by the author (2025).

Here, sound is no longer tensioned material, but residue, a suspended trace. Gesture is reduced to a minimum, time stretches, and the sonic surface is transformed into a kind of ash, a timbral dust that retains the echo of what once was. Inspired by Burri’s painting and his use of wood, where lacerations accumulate into opaque strata, this section too sees sound losing volume yet gaining depth, moving within an interior space shaped more by absences than by presences

The timbral writing assumes an almost ritual quality. The woodwinds employ extended techniques, such as using the bow hair on the body of the instrument and later striking the wood, while the winds produce key clicks and breath sounds. The bass drum serves as a material support for an acoustic energy that is low in intensity yet rich in perceptual density. The sound is muted, opaque, and granular, resembling a charred sonic body that resists silence (Fig.10). The texture is pointillistic but not disjointed. It is a fire that continues to burn, even within the near absence of gesture, where each sonic micro event seems to dig inward, opening a perceptual space that is both deep and concentrated (Fig.11-12).

Figure 10. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.22, Score by the author (2025).

Figure 11. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.23, Score by the author (2025).

Figure 12. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.28, Score by the author (2025).

It is within this context that, beginning at measure 86, the pitches assigned to the soprano from Monteverdi's *Lamento d'Arianna* begin to surface from the piano, scattered and discrete (Fig.13).

Figure 13.C. Monteverdi, *Lamento d'Arianna*, from "Madrigali guerrieri et amorosi", Book VIII, Venice, 1638. Public domain edition available at IMLSP – Petrucci Music Library, accessed October 2025.

The fragment reemerges in a newly transformed sonic configuration. Broken down into minimal units, reduced to discontinuous segments, and distributed through a pointillistic mode of writing, it loses its original linear coherence and takes on the form of a fractured, almost sublimated echo. This echo, in the piano part, insinuates itself into the musical fabric as a deformed mnemonic trace, revealing a process of perceptual reworking that operates at the level of interrupted memory and disintegrated temporality (Fig.14).

Figure 14. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, bar 86, Score by the author (2025).

The entire process thus takes shape as a measured accumulation of latent energy, a progressive construction of emptiness that prepares the emergence of a restrained climax. The flame rises, briefly expands within the acoustic space, and is then extinguished, leaving behind an active silence charged with potential tension (Fig. 15-16).

Figure 15. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.29, Score by the author (2025).

Figure 16. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.30, Score by the author (2025).

Within this rarefied space, the trumpet enters with delicacy yet with firmness, not as a heroic element but as a voice that opens a breach, a luminous fissure within the density of darkness. It is a gesture of transition, one that does not conclude but guides, preparing the entry of the following section as a passage beyond the abyss, as a fragile and inexorable emergence (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.31, Score by the author (2025).

The third and final section of *Abissum II (racines)* represents the symbolic and formal culmination of the compositional journey. It is a slow ascent from the burned matter toward a region of fragile and unstable light, where memory, echo, and time merge into a layered perceptual continuum. With the agogic indication *luminoso*, the harmonic discourse unfolds as an ascending chromatic scale, a gradual vertical motion that resists the gravitational weight evoked in the first part of the work. Yet this ascent is neither linear nor triumphant, for the writing is continuously marked by oscillating tension and by an orchestral restlessness that recalls earlier musical styles.

This sonic ascent carries with it residual traces, fragments that resurface like ghosts of sound. In particular, the gesture at measure 120, later reworked in a more elaborate form at measure 125, reduced to an incipit at bar 128, and finally resumed in its essential form at measure 139, constitutes a surface echo that affirms itself as a living and immediate memory (Fig.18).

Figure 18. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, bars 120,125,128,139, Score by the Author

The reference to the opening of the third movement of *Professor Bad Trip - Lesson I* by Fausto Romitelli is crucial in this context. The gesture, so characteristic of Romitelli, clear, incisive, cuts through the musical material as a spectral presence, a different level of sonic consciousness, positioned on an exposed and almost epidermal plane, with a violence that contrasts sharply with the deeper and more rarefied texture into which it is embedded.

Moreover, the fragment under consideration reemerges as a structural memory of its own earlier appearance within the score, specifically between measures 48, 52, 62, and 69. It appears there in a configuration that is stylistically reminiscent of the language of Gesualdo, marked by intense chromaticism, intervallic discontinuity, and a tense contrapuntal articulation. Its recurrence in transformed guise is not a mere thematic restatement, but instead activates a compositional mechanism grounded in temporal layering. The listener is called upon to recognise a fragmented identity that functions simultaneously as return and as refraction a process of internal memory that imparts formal depth and perceptual tension to the unfolding of the sonic discourse.

What follows is a turn toward a state of controlled orchestral delirium, in which the writing becomes dense, ornate, and whirling. The ascent gives way to a timbral frenzy, an ambiguous space between illumination and collapse, where tension reaches its highest point before emptying into the final gesture.

It is at this moment that the true transfiguration of time and memory takes place. Sound contracts and gradually fades, like a wave, evoked explicitly by the gesture of the percussion brush drawn across the skin of the bass drum (Fig.19-20).

Figure 19. Excerpt from *Abissum II (racines)*, p.51, Score by the Author

Figure 20. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), p.53, Score by the Author

This makes way for the wordless song, which serves simultaneously as threshold and epilogue, as memory and body, as echo and silence.

It is in the conclusion of the composition that the pitches of the melodic fragment drawn from Monteverdi's *Lamento d'Arianna* are reemployed in the form of a wordless song, sung with closed mouth. Its ascending line stands as a mirror inversion of the original descending version associated with the famous opening phrase *Lasciatemi morire*. This reversal of direction, stripped of text but not of expressive weight, generates an opposing semantic resonance. Through the melodic gesture alone, it suggests an affirmative tension that stands in contrast to the tragic dimension of the Monteverdian source (Fig.21).

Figure 21. Excerpt from Abissum II (racines), bar 205, Score by the Author

In this final moment, the composition does not conclude but suspends; it does not resolve but holds. Time does not end, but is heard from another place, a space in which memory is no longer a distinction between before and after, but a coexistence of exposed surfaces and buried depths, of living fragments and consumed matter, of light and shadow intertwined.

6. Conclusions: Sound Memory and the Dramaturgy of Time. A Compositional Perspective

The three analyses presented here, namely the third movement of *Sinfonia* by Luciano Berio, *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco* by Jonathan Harvey, and *Abissum II (racines)* as a personal compositional case study, represent distinct yet profoundly interconnected perspectives on a single poetic nucleus: musical time understood as a field of resonance for sound memory. In each of these works, memory does not merely resurface as recollection but operates as formal structure, dramaturgical gesture, and perceptual space, determining not only the morphology of sound but also the way it is experienced. Memory is therefore not simply content, but a compositional act, a generative principle, a latent energy that constructs sonic architectures through the stratification of echoes, returns, fragments, and transformations.

In *Sinfonia*, Berio composes through the memory of the repertoire, transforming historical material into a living gesture and a perceptual dramaturgy. The musical past, exemplified by Mahler, Debussy, Beckett, and Joyce, is no longer an archive but a stratified presence that inscribes itself in time as tension, collision, and interference. In *Mortuos Plango, Vivos Voco*, Harvey creates a sonic landscape in which memory fuses with timbre, generating an acoustic continuum where voice and bell pursue each other as temporal archetypes, shaping a cyclical, spiritual, and ritual perception of time. Both works share a conception of sound as a historicised material that never exists in isolation, but always as part of a network of references, gestures, and spectres.

Abissum II (racines) enters this trajectory with a radically personal position. It is a composition that absorbs and transforms the principles discussed, integrating them into a poetics that conceives sound not as sign but as living matter to be traversed, wounded, and transfigured. In this perspective, sound memory becomes a topology of listening, an uneven and heterogeneous space in which returns are never identical but rather altered traces, distorted sources, and remnants. The references to Gesualdo, Monteverdi, Romitelli, and to the composer's own earlier work (*Abissum I*) unfold across multiple levels of depth and exposure, generating a form built upon mnemonic stratification, where time is never linear but a dynamic fabric of emergences and disappearances.

This dramaturgical conception of memory as a gesture of time is also reflected in the compositional writing itself. Extended techniques, pointillistic textures, prepared sounds, and muted and irregular sonorities act as corporeal modalities of time. Sound behaves like an organism that remembers, not through repetition but through mutation, accumulation, and loss. Musical time thus becomes an embodied experience, a perceptual form in constant motion, a field of forces between what has been, what is, and what may still emerge.

Ultimately, to conceive sound memory as a dramaturgy of time does not merely mean to rethink the past, but to redefine the relationship between composition and listening, between gesture and perception. It implies recognizing that listening is always an interpretative, archaeological, and stratified act, and that musical performance is a space of rewriting in which every sound is memory made manifest and every echo a form in becoming. In this sense, musical time is not a simple dimension in which sound unfolds, but a sensitive substance shaped through memory, finding in composition and performance its acts of resistance, transformation, and truth.

The trajectory opened by these reflections does not end with the closure of the work. On the contrary, it delineates a critical and poetic horizon still to be explored. The ways in which memory can act upon time, traversing sound, form, and listening, constitute an ongoing compositional and aesthetic inquiry, an open space in which the past is composed as a present gesture rather than merely evoked, a living and interior form of time itself.

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